

APPENDIX 1: SURVEY ITEMS

M1 - I find pleasure in improving quality of the environment by reducing environmental damage.

M2 - Taking care of the environment has become part of the way I have chosen to live my life

M3 - I have chosen to contribute to a better environment by doing something myself

M4 - I care for the environment to avoid being criticized

M6 - I would give part of my income if I were certain that the money would be used to prevent environmental pollution

M7 - I would agree to an increase in taxes if the extra money were used to prevent environmental pollution

M8 - I would agree to contribute to the environment, but it should not come at a cost to me.

A1 - I am aware that spending more time on the internet can increase my environmental impact

A2 - I am aware that higher data usage in internet activities can lead to greater environmental damage

A3 - I am aware that playing online games can contribute to greenhouse gas emissions

A4 - I am aware that online shopping can have a negative impact on the environment

A5 - I am aware that using social media can contribute to environmental harm

A6 - I am aware that using ChatGPT and similar AI tools increases energy demand on data centers, negatively impacting the environment

IU1 - On average, how often did you use the internet for social media purposes the past month? (scrolling on social media, watching videos, posting or viewing content)

IU2 - On average, how often did you use the internet for e-commerce purposes the past month? (e-commerce platforms such as Temu or using social media to purchase products or sign yourself up for competitions, giveaways etc)

IU3 - On average, how often did you use the internet for GenAI purposes the past month? (e.g ChatGPT)

IU4 - On average, how often did you use the internet for gaming purposes the past month?

APPENDIX 2: A SUMMARY OF DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS

Gender	#	%	Industry	#	%
Male	88	44%	Information Technology/Software Development	53	27%
Female	109	55%	Health	34	17%
Other	3	1%	Engineering/Manufacturing	18	9%
			Economics & Finance	13	7%
			Agriculture/Forestry/Fishing	9	4%
Age	#	%	Legal	4	2%
18-29	85	43%			
30-44	83	42%	Other	69	34%
45-65	29	14%			
66+	3	1%	Device most used to access internet	#	%
			Smartphone/tablets	107	54%
			Laptop/ desktop computers	93	46%
Country of residence	#	%			
South Africa	63	32%			
United States	43	21%			
Canada	18	9%			
United Kingdom	16	8%			
Other	60	30%			

APPENDIX 3: MODEL FIT COMPARISON TABLE

Model	AIC	BIC	Entropy	BLRT p-value	Smallest class %	Model Interpretation
2-class	2093.55	2234.61	0.78	-	47%	Classes not clearly differentiated; over-generalised patterns
3-class	2067.52	2242.34	0.82	0.001	13%	Good class separation
4-class	2060.47	2278.31	0.80	0.005	7.6%	Slight AIC improvement but small unstable class; limited interpretive value

APPENDIX 4: LCA RESULTS

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$InternetUse
      Pr(1) Pr(2) Pr(3) Pr(4)
class 1: 0.1530 0.4351 0.2056 0.2064
class 2: 0.0000 0.5334 0.3500 0.1166
class 3: 0.2427 0.4646 0.1043 0.1885

$AutonomousM
      Pr(1) Pr(2) Pr(3) Pr(4) Pr(5)
class 1: 0.1147 0.6108 0.2744 0.0000 0.0000
class 2: 0.0000 0.0341 0.1788 0.5250 0.2621
class 3: 0.0000 0.0220 0.0000 0.3461 0.6320

$ControlledM
      Pr(1) Pr(2) Pr(3) Pr(4) Pr(5)
class 1: 0.1147 0.7012 0.1841 0.0000 0.0000
class 2: 0.0000 0.2675 0.4993 0.2332 0.0000
class 3: 0.0000 0.0000 0.2753 0.6573 0.0674

$Awareness
      Pr(1) Pr(2) Pr(3) Pr(4) Pr(5)
class 1: 0.3065 0.4209 0.0000 0.2081 0.0645
class 2: 0.0350 0.2648 0.4295 0.2279 0.0428
class 3: 0.1415 0.1834 0.1778 0.4158 0.0815

Estimated class population shares
0.1307 0.4984 0.3709

Predicted class memberships (by modal posterior prob.)
0.135 0.525 0.34

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Fit for 3 latent classes:
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number of observations: 200
number of estimated parameters: 47
residual degrees of freedom: 153
maximum log-likelihood: -995.4062 |

AIC(3): 2084.812
BIC(3): 2239.833
G^2(3): 225.0803 (Likelihood ratio/deviance statistic)
X^2(3): 553.71 (Chi-square goodness of fit)
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